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The Shrine, Mosque and Church in the Pluralistic Nigerian Society: Challenges and Way Forward

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Abstract

It is no gainsaying that Nigeria is a pluralistic country in terms of religion and culture. It is also unarguable that among the religions in the country, traditional religion, Islam and Christianity are the most officially recognised. The interface, interlock and interaction among these triadic religions have been investigated by previous scholars. The joint collaboration of Islam and Christianity against traditional religion has equally been demonstrated theoretically but not empirically, which is the gap this paper intends to fill. Having explained the terms mosque, church, shrine and pluralism and how they are to be construed, the paper discusses the interface, interlock and interaction among the

triadic religions. Moreover, survey research method was adopted to poll opinions of 45 randomly selected respondents (consisting of Muslims, Christians and traditionalists) on the religious, economic, political and social attitudes of Islam and Christianity against traditional religion in the contemporary pluralistic Nigerian society. Data were analysed by means of mean rating with 2.5 as the criterion mean. Findings reveal that many Muslims and Christians still treat traditionalists as pagans in our contemporary pluralistic Nigerian society. Some Muslims and Christians patronise traditional practitioners for economic improvement and welfare. Many Muslims and Christians prefer people of their own religious groups rather than traditionalists to be appointed into public offices. Many Muslims and Christians would not send their children to the emerging traditional faith-based schools. It was suggested, among other things, that Nigerians should imbibe the national ethical principle of religious tolerance; and love one another irrespective of tribe and religion.

Keywords: Shrine, Mosques, Church, Pluralistic Nigerian Society

Introduction

Before the advent of foreign religions in Black Africa, traditional religion (or, African Indigenous/traditional Religion) was the only religion of the indigenous people on the continent, and thus could be described as a virgin religion because it was free from contaminations by foreign religions. Traditional religion is both heterogeneous as well as homogenous as Black African people. Its heterogeneity indicates the diverse brands traditional religion on African continent (which informs the idea of pluralisation of the name in some scholarly circle) whereas its homogeneity indicates the similarity in diversity of traditional religions (which informs the singularisation of the name as it is used in this paper). Unlike foreign religions of Christianity and Islam, traditional religion is dateless because it is as old as the history of African people. Traditional religion, according to Omoleye (2012), is the ancient or age-old traditional religion of West African people which evolved with creation of the universe. This is why it is called, in Yoruba parlance, *Esin Isembaye* or *Isedale*. It is the religion of the indigenous people of West Africa which recognises one God with a diversity of divinities/gods (known as *Orisa* in Yoruba parlance) performing His creative functions in different places under different names and conditions (Omoleye, 2012).

In African theogony, the divinities and spirits are emanations of the Supreme Being (called *Olodumare* in Yoruba parlance). Omoleye (2012)

distinguishes between divinities and spirits by asserting that the former were full emanations while the latter were lesser emanations. To Adeoye (1987), divinities and spirits are full emanations of *Olodumare* but the sacrifices of the former (divinities) were accepted in Skye heaven before coming to the earth while the sacrifices of the latter (spirits) were not acceptable before their sojourn on the earth. The two authors, however, agree that the divinities were the fore-runners of humanity and the intermediaries between man and the Supreme Being. Besides God, divinities and spirits, other pillars of AIR, according to Idowu (1973), are ancestral worship and practice of magic and medicine. While Idowu prefer to call traditional religion a diffused monotheist religion, other authors such as Adeoye (1987), Awolalu and Dopamu (1979), Daramola and Jeje (1975) refer to it as a strict monotheist religion. However, it is the opinion of this paper that henotheism (recognition of different deities among which only one is the Supreme Being) seem to be a better term for describing the religion. Traditional religion is passed from generation to generation in an unbroken chain of unpolluted transition until the advents of Islam and Christianity in Black Africa (West African to be precise).

As indicated earlier, Nigeria was an exclusive society where only traditional religion, deities and their shrines thrived before the advents of Islam with mosque and Christianity with church in Africa. Traditional religion was the exclusive religion of Black Africa while the shrine was the only sacred place of worship. The traditional religion, deities and shrines were regarded very highly and reverently by all and was patronised by all. Whenever shrine was sited, it was indeed a sacred place of worship of the gods and goddesses of the land. It is approached with awe and reverent fear by children, youths, parents, family/clan heads, chiefs, kings and cultic priests. The shrine, according to Jegede (2015), is a sacred place because it is the place of meeting between people and their traditional deities. Presence of the deities is what sanctifies and sacralises the shrine just as the presence of the king sanctifies the palace; otherwise the shrine is no different from any other place. The close association between the shrines and deities, or traditional religion, or traditionalists is what has informed the metonymous use of shrine to mean traditional religion/traditionalists in this paper.

Traditional religion, deities and their shrines were accorded full respect in Africa before the advents of the mosque and church as no one viewed the shrines as the abode of non-existent or false or dead gods/goddesses. Some

of the functions of the shrine (then and now) include being a place of worship, education, oath taking, dispute settlement, moral sanction or punishment or judgement (Jegade, 2015). Cultic priests were the mouthpiece of the deities. They were equally feared, respected and valued by Africans until the advent of Islam and Christianity, which marked the beginning of religious pluralism in Black Africa, or West Africa to be precise. Before the advents of Islam and Christianity in West Africa, Nigeria is less pluralised in terms of religion. That the plurality of the Nigerian society is partly encouraged by Islam, Christianity, colonisation, and western education has been demonstrated by scholar such as Ikenga-Metuh (1986). With the advents of Islam and Christianity came so many other religions, thus making Nigeria a multi-religious society, or religious pluralistic society or a secular state. The question of which of the foreign religions is most hostile to AIR has been substantiated in scholarly discourse by Malefijt (1968) and Trimmingham (1959). Christianity (which is predated by Islam) is unanimously identified as the most hostile to traditional religion. Islam is next to Christianity in this regard. The interface, interlock and interactions among the triadic religious institutions namely mosque, church and shrine (which, in the context of this paper, mean Muslims, Christians and traditionalists rather than their places of worship) in the pluralistic Nigerian society is one of the concerns of this paper.

Unlike the institution of Islam with mosque (which had been well entrenched in Nigeria from the time of the Jihad of Uthman Dan Fodio), it is on record that the institution of Christianity with church were aided by colonialism in its bid not only to compete with Islam but also to subdue the traditional religion and culture, or, if possible, extirpate it. The religion and culture of the colonial masters who were at the helms of affairs in Black Africa thrived because wielder of political power is more positioned for success in any form of confrontation. Moreover, the original African systems, especially religious, political and economic systems, were replaced with foreign ones by both the church and colonial masters via the strategies of condemnation, stigmatization, discrimination, persecution, which attracted some confrontations and resistance by the traditionalists. Consequently, many of the adherents of traditional religions embraced either Islam or Christianity. Some of these converts became over-zealous to the point of not only preaching against their native religions but also desecrating, destroying and looting traditional sacred places, especially the shrines.

Since then, Islam and Christianity have dominated the pluralistic Nigeria religious space.

Since the invasion of Yorubaland and the rest of Nigeria by Islam and Christianity, traditional religion has been derogated and persecuted by the adherents of Islam and Christianity with a view to exterminate it. By way of reaction or self-preservation, traditionalists have sometimes been on the offensive rather than defensive against Islam and Christianity. However, Derogatory terms and extirpation attempts from these two Abrahamic religions on traditional religion have been noted by scholars such Idowu (1973) and Ikenga-Metuh (1986). Moreover, observation reveals that social hostility (in forms of marginalisation, discrimination, persecution, stigmatization, name-calling, contempt, intolerance, etc) still exists between mosque and church, mosque and shrine as well as church and shrine. The mosque and church (in their exclusive dogma) seems to abhor the shrines while the latter seems to tolerate the former, perhaps, due to its inclusive dogma. However, what this paper intends to investigate is what Dopamu (1986) called the “joint institution of collaboration” of mosques and church against the shrine in the contemporary pluralised Nigerian society.

Four research questions are raised in a bid to investigate this “joint institution of collaboration” observation. What is the religious attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society? What is the economic attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society? What is the political attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society? What is the social attitude of the mosques and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society? Based on random sampling method, answers to the questions were elicited from 15 Muslims, 15 Christians and 15 traditionalists in Ibadan land via researcher-designed questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using mean rating with criterion mean of 2.5. Meanwhile, the paper clarifies the terms mosques, church, shrine and pluralism; it reviews literature on patterns of interaction between traditional religion, Islam, Christianity and, and finally answers the research questions and conclude with pertinent recommendations.

Pluralism and Pluralistic Nigerian Society

The research variable of this paper namely *pluralistic Nigerian society* deserves elaboration. Pluralism as a term implies multiplicity, variety,

diversity, differentiations, and non-monotony. Pluralism could be applied to anything, most especially nature, religion and culture. Nigeria is a pluralistic society in that there are religious and cultural diversities in the country. Supporting pluralism, Alamu (2010) has demonstrated Dopamu's thesis that God loves variety and hates monotony, specifically with respect to religion. Dopamu's argument, according to Alamu (2010), is that just as there is variety/diversity among plants, fish, birds, animals and human beings and the Creator of these varied items is believed to be God, so also should the variety in religion (among mankind) be construed as the handiwork of God. Since God is behind the variety in all (living) religions in the world, then all religions must co-exist peacefully. Thus, peaceful inter-faith or inter-cultural co-existence is the cardinal doctrine of pluralism.

Taking a clue from Umejiesi and Igboin (2010), there are four types of society: the exclusive, inclusive, pluralistic and parallelistic societies. The exclusive society is where variety in religion and culture is forbidden. It is a mono religious and mono cultural society. Such type of society seems to belong to history as no modern society can be called exclusive society. Inclusive society is one where variety in religion and culture are tolerated but the native religion and culture is regarded as the best. Examples of this type of society in modern time include Islamic countries like Saudi Arabia, Iran, Iraq, and Syria. Pluralistic society is one where variety in religion and culture is regarded as fundamental human right of every member of the society. A pluralistic society is a secular state. Variety in religion and culture is not only tolerated but also celebrated in a pluralistic society. However, it is still possible to find some religion and culture to be more dominant in such society. Nigeria is an example of this. Parallelistic society is where variety in religion and culture is a fundamental human right and where every religion and culture has same or equal status before the law. It is a society where no religion or culture is inferior or superior to another. Thus, each religion and culture is parallel or equal before the law. No partiality, discrimination, stigmatization, marginalisation and persecution on the basis of religion and culture. The United States of America is a good example of a parallelistic society.

Mosques

Muslims pray in a place of worship called the mosque. A mosque is called a *masjid* in Arabic (Watchtower Tract and Bible Society, 1990). Muslims take

their shoes off before entering the *masjid* to pray. Prayer is one of the most important things that a Muslim does. A large mosque for gathering for Friday prayers or Eid prayers are called *masjid jāmi*. Although the primary purpose of the mosque is to serve as a place of prayer, it is also important to the Muslim community as a place to meet and study; a place of legal and judicial activities, consultation, preaching, guidance, education and preparation (Watchtower Tract and Bible Society, 1990). In Medina, *Al-Masjid al-Nabawi*, or the Prophet's Mosque, was also a place of refuge for the poor. Modern mosques have evolved greatly from the early designs of the 7th century, and contain a variety of architectural elements such as minarets.

Within the context of Nigeria, Muslim denominations are essentially four: the Sunni, Shias, Sufism and the Ahmadiyyah. The largest denomination in Islam is Sunni Islam which makes up 75%–90% of all Muslims (Watchtower Tract and Bible Society. 1990) who believe that the first four caliphs were the rightful successors to Muhammad; since God did not specify any particular leaders to succeed him. The Shia constitutes 10–20% of Islam and is its second-largest branch (Watchtower Tract and Bible Society. 1990). Rejecting the legitimacy of previous Muslim caliphs, Shi'a Muslims believe that God chose Ali as the leader after Muhammad. The Sufi is a branch in Islam that focuses more on the spiritual and mystic elements of Islam. Ahmadiyya is an Islamic reform movement (with Sunni roots) founded by Mirza Ghulam Ahmad that began in India in 1889 and is practiced by 10 to 20 million Muslims around the world (Gardet,1961). However, Mosque, in the context of this paper, means Islam or the different denomination of Muslims in Nigeria; or Nigerian Muslim community (*Ummah*) in general.

Church

Church as a term has two levels of meanings: the gathering of people (here, emphasis is on human being) and the building in which the people gathered (here, emphasis is on physical structure). To elaborate, the term refers to the gathering of people in the name of Christ or people who are associated with the name of Jesus Christ who they claim as their Lord and Saviour in particular and Saviour of the entire human race is general. Jesus Christ is also acclaimed as the mediator between God and human being. Evidently, these set of people are found in different denominations within the Nigerian Christendom such that we can safely take the term to connote Christians

found within Mainline/Mission churches, African Independents churches and Pentecostal churches in Nigeria. Church as a term also means the physical buildings where these people congregate in the name of Christ. Some of these buildings are like mansion or palace; some are like town halls while others are like mushroom shops. It is believed that this physical building is a sacred place where the people meet with their Lord and Saviour. Hence, it is essentially a place of worship. Nigerians are familiar with these two levels of meanings. But in the context of this paper, church represents Christianity or Nigerian Christian community.

Shrine

Shrine as a term specifically refers to a sacred place where the traditionalists (adherents of African traditional religion) congregate in the name of *Orisa* (divinities cum spirits) who they believe to be divine messengers of the Supreme Being (called *Olodumare* in Yoruba religion). Compared to mosque and church, shrines are very simple in structure and limited in space. Shrines could be in a room, in front of the house, backyard of the house, in King's palaces, near road junction or crossroad, near the bush or in the bush (such as sacred groove). The simplistic nature and limited geographical space of shrines informs terms such as individual shrines, family/clan shrine, and community/town shrines. Unlike church, traditionalists are not known as shrine. The term strictly refers to the sacred place of traditional worship. However, and within the context of this paper, shrine represents traditional religion or traditionalists.

Mosque, Church and Shrine: The Interface, Interlock and Interaction

As places of worship, the terms mosque, church and shrine are basically similar in that they refer to sacred places of worship where the physical, tangible and secular meets with the spiritual, intangible and sacred. They are places where the sensible and natural world engages the super-sensible and super-natural world in reverence and worship. Thus, shrine is parallel to mosques and church in essence and value. If real contextualisation is contemplated, what is called mosque or church should have been called shrine (*oju ibo* in Yoruba parlance). This is a more appropriate English translation of mosque and church in Yoruba context. Shrines as *oju ibo* means the spots where the *Orisa* (messengers of the supreme Being) are worshipped, or venerated. However, this does not mean that *Orisa* worship

is idolatry as claimed by adherents of foreign religions. African traditional theology avers that divinities cum spirits have *direct contact* with the Supreme Being who in turn had commissioned them to act as His messengers or intermediaries in matters of sacrifices and worship which is eventually passed on to Him. In other words, divinities cum spirits not only accept sacrifices and worship of Africans, they in turn pass it on to the Supreme Being for acceptance and final approval. Hence, as Africans worship/venerate the divinities cum spirits, they in turn worship the Supreme Being. However, the fact that African traditional theology asserts that the Supreme Being accepts human worship *Orisa* worship does not imply that Africans cannot approach God or pray to God directly.

The point being made is that, to African traditionalists, *Orisa* worship is an indirect worship of the Supreme Being. In fact, as messengers of *Olodumare*, *Orisa* accept Yoruba African worship on behalf of *Olodumare* (Awolalu and Dopamu, 1979). Thus, *Olodumare*, in the traditional Yoruba theology, does not forbid *Orisa* worship, hence, He is not a jealous God like the Bible/Christian God who forbids angelic/idol worship because He is a jealous God. The traditional concept of *Olodumare* as a transcendent Being who could be reached via the *Orisa* for a more efficacious results is another justification for *Orisa* worship (Olupona and Falola, 1991). Shrine is a spot where *Orisa* are fed with the sacrifice of bloody and non-bloody items for acceptance by them and the Supreme Being whereas mosque and church are spots where Allah and God/Christ are fed with the sacrifice of prayer, praise and worship respectively. Therefore, just as shrine is *oju ibo* for the traditionalists, mosque and church are *oju ibo* for the Muslims and Christians respectively.

Another interface is that traditionalists, Muslims and Christians are believers in the Supreme Being. For detailed example of the theological or doctrinal interface between the triadic religions, Nabofa's (1991) table (reproduced below) is germane.

Table 1: The Theological or Doctrinal Interface Between the Triadic Religions

S/N	African Traditional Religion	Islam	Christianity
1.	Belief in a Supreme Being with different names and attributes	Belief in a Supreme Being known as Allah with 99 names.	Belief in a Supreme Being called Jehovah, Elohim, Lord, God.

	in different African cultures.		
2.	Belief in various grades of divinities; primordial deities, deified personalities, and divinities associated with natural elements such as the sun, thunder and lightning.	Belief in Angels and Archangels, each with specific functions.	Belief in Angels and Archangels, each with special functions.
3.	Belief in Spirit which are lesser and undomesticated, having no shrines established for them.	Belief in Spirits, called <i>jinn</i> , and Satan.	Belief in Spirits of various temperaments, including Satan.
4.	Belief in life after death, which is the basis of the cult of ancestors.	Belief in Saints and Holy men such as the Caliphs of the first generation.	Belief in Saints, especially the Twelve Apostles.
5.	Belief in Mysterious Powers, including witchcraft, sorcery and efficacy of magic and medicine.	Belief in charms, Tira and kabalistic principles.	Belief in the use and efficacy of psalms, use of the cross in exorcism, incense with kabalistic principles and holy oil and water.
6.	Eschatology: the just are happily reunited with the Ancestors at the end of life and are reincarnated into the same family; the wicked are driven out and become bands of wandering and disgruntled spirits lamenting their fate.	Eschatology: the righteous go to enjoy eternal bliss in Heaven, while the unjust go Hellfire.	Eschatology: the righteous enter into the kingdom of God in Heaven, to enjoy eternal bliss with God and all the host of Saints and Angels; the wicked suffer in Hellfire.
7.	Cultic functionaries: High Priests	Caliphs and Imams	Pope, Bishops, pastors.

The interlock among these triadic religions is that they are living religions. A living religion is one that has adherents. Hence, traditional religion, Islam and Christianity are living religions in the pluralistic Nigerian society. The first predated the last two. It was exclusively practiced before the advents of the last two. Islam also predated Christianity. Ever since, the two religions have become rivals. However, they usually conspire to extirpate traditional religion but usually fail in that traditional religion is not extinct but still living till date with much virility. However, both have succeeded in modifying traditional religion a great deal, which in turn have influenced them somewhat.

The interactions among these triadic religions have been discussed in detail by Dopamu (1986) who stated that Islam and Christianity were jointly hostile to traditional religion, which, on the other hand, was very open-minded and accommodative to all religions. Traditional religion is friendly and accommodative because it recognises other cults and divinities in other religions (Islam and Christianity inclusive) as part of the whole Ultimate Reality. Moreover, these foreign religions were distrustful of each other; they dislike or contempt each other and were hostile to each other. Dopamu (1986) and Adeyeri (2005) blame the intense rivalry/conflict between Islam and Christianity on their exclusive claims or particularism. He also identifies their methods of conversion to be another cause of conflict. Hence, he describes their methods of conversion as “crude and unspiritual” because they are characterised by acrimony, bitterness, hostility, and even bloodshed. More specifically, he asserts that Muslims and Christians regard each other as pagans who are worst than the traditionalists.

Dopamu (1986) notes that, while Islam and Christianity are fond of fighting each other, they usually collaborate (instinctively) in fighting traditional religion. But Christianity, according to him and in agreement with Trimmingham (1959), is more hostile to traditional religion than Islam. Their joint hostility to traditional religion made the author to assert that Islam and Christianity operate “in joint institutions of collaboration” in condemning traditional religion by use of derogatory terms to describe its adherents. Sometimes, Muslims or Christians go to the extent of destroying sacred traditional objects and places, which usually provoke originally friendly traditionalists to start persecuting them. Casting aspersion on traditional religion, the duo of Islam and Christianity scramble for converts among traditionalists and usually win many. Reasons for acceptance of

either Islam or Christianity as highlighted by Dopamu (1986) include personal gain, political ambition, selfish ends, egocentricity, power for domination, ethnicity, special appeal, admiration and spiritual satisfaction, marriage, friendship and freedom from obnoxious traditional practices. The mundaneness of many of these reasons indicates why many of the so-called converts are compromisers and syncretise believers.

Islam, according to Dopamu (1986), was particularly attractive to the traditionalists because it (Islam) admired certain cultural practices (like polygamy and use of some traditional medicine and magic) and even condones them whereas Christianity condemned all cultural practices in unmistakable terms. Reacting to the hostility of Christianity to Africism (Encyclopedia of African Religion. London: SAGE) , Africa Yoruba Christians, armed with the belief that Christianity should be practiced within the cultural context of the Africa in order for it to be meaningful, floated African independent churches which adopted/adapted many values in traditional religion to enhance African Christianity.

Dopamu (1986) highlights mission strategies for the promotion of Christianity in Yorubaland in particular. These include, among others, African independent churches, indigenisation policy (which made African leaders to assume leadership of Mission churches), triumph of western education, use of schools, hospitals and technical/vocational training centres. He notes that schools, in particular, were most successful in the propagation of the tenets of Christianity. Before government-take-over of mission schools, children of both Muslims and Traditionalists attended these schools where Christian religious instruction was taught. Many children of the traditionalists and a few of Muslim children became converted to Christianity.

Although relationship between Islam and Christianity remains competitive yet there are areas of cooperation between them on the one hand, and between them and traditional religion on the other hand. Specific areas of cooperation among the triadic religions, as demonstrated by Dopamu (1987), include cooperation in village communal work, extended family system, religious festivals, trade, association, education, government, politics, industries, and so on. Adherents of the triadic religions participate and interact in the aforementioned areas either at the level of dialogue of life, dialogue of social engagement, dialogue of religious experience, or dialogue of theological engagement.

These patterns of interaction, among other things, have made possible a great deal of inter-religious exchange/borrowing. Some elements of traditional religion have been adapted by Islam and Christianity. Specific examples of areas of such adaptations, according to Dopamu (1986), include Muslim divination and sacrifice (known as *saara*, that is, free offering), drumming, singing, clapping and dancing in churches, use of traditional materials (like alligator pepper, kolanut, bitter kola, water, honey, red-oil, etc) in some Christian naming ceremony, and patronisation of Yoruba magic and medicine men (called thaumaturgical response).

Islam and Christianity have also borrowed from each other. For instance, Ahmadiya have copied Christian Pentecostal churches in mode of worship. Some Muslim marriages are now conducted as Christian marriages, the only difference being the use of Quran instead of the Bible. Dopamu (1986) further demonstrates the facts that compromise, financial assistance and religious programmes are other areas of interactions among the triadic religions. Compromise, according to the author, refers to the situation where a Muslim or Christian is also a traditionalist or practice traditional religion as occasion demands. Marriage as a form of interaction refers to the situation where a Muslim marries a Christian or traditionalist. Financial assistance is an area of interaction because it is no gainsaying that people of different faith seek financial assistance from one another. Religious programmes are another area of interaction because some Muslim attends Christian revivals where miracles are purported to be performed. Some Christian also attends Muslim programmes. In view of the foregoing, the author concludes that Islam and Christianity only succeeded in modifying traditional religion but not in extirpating it.

Nabofa (1991) has also indicated the interactions among the triadic religions by demonstrating the areas of continuity of traditional religion in Islam and Christianity. Areas of continuity of traditional religion in Islam and Christianity include marriage, naming ceremony and procreation; divination, sacrifice and exorcism; externalisation of problem; role of women; honours and chieftaincy; dress of priest and the people; harvest thanksgiving; manner of cursing and blessing; cult of ancestors; wake-keeping and funeral service; symbolism in worship; Muslim and Christian liturgies; prayer; use of medicine and magic; predestination and re-incarnation; retribution; attitude towards wealth; evangelisation methods; institutional nomenclature; and participation in traditional festivals. In

other words, the foregoing items have been engrafted with elements of traditional religion and practices.

Data Presentation and Analysis

To investigate the “joint institution of collaboration” of mosque and church against the shrine, the earlier raised four research questions are now answered in this section using mean rating with criterion mean of 2.5, which indicate respondents’ disagreement (if the mean value of an item is *less than* 2.5) and respondents’ agreement (if the mean value of an item is *equal to or greater than* 2.5). Each research question has five moderating variables/items, making a total of twenty items.

Research Question 1: What is the religious attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society?

Table 2: Mean Rating of Respondents’ Opinions on Religious Attitude in the pluralistic Nigerian society

N=45

s/no	Muslim and Christian religious attitudes to traditionalists	Mean rating)	Response			(mean Total
	Item description	T	M	C	Total	
1.	Many Muslims and Christians treat traditionalists as pagans.	3.94	3.50	3.50	10.94	
2.	Many Muslims and Christians regard traditional religion as a dead religion.	3.06	3.50	3.83	10.39	
3.	Many Muslims and Christians consider traditional religion as something to be eradicated from the face of the earth, if possible.	3.56	2.83	3.17	9.56	
4.	Many Muslims and Christians preach against traditional religion.	3.16	3.53	3.78	10.47	
5.	Some Muslims or Christians are also traditionalists or practice traditional religion as occasion demands.	3.81	2.97	2.53	9.31	

3.50 3.26 3.36 10.13

Grand mean

Key: T=Traditionalist, M=Muslim, C= Christian

Based on the criterion mean of 2.5, it is clear from Table 2 that no item has mean value or grand mean value below 2.5, which means that members of the triadic religions agreed or strongly agreed that items 1 to 5 are indeed manifest religious attitude to traditionalists in the pluralistic Nigerian society. However, item 1 (with cumulative mean value of 10.94) is the leading religious attitude of Muslims and Christians to traditionalists. The grand means further indicate that there is no significant difference in the opinions of these triadic religious believers in this regard.

Research Question 2: What is the economic attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society?

Table 3: Mean Rating of Respondents’ Opinions on Economic Attitude in the pluralistic Nigerian society

N=45

s/no	Muslim and Christian economic attitudes to traditionalists	Mean Response (Mean rating)			
	Item description	T	M	C	Total
1.	Many Muslims and Christians would rather assist people of their own religious groups than meeting the economic needs of the traditionalists.	3.41	3.25	3.50	10.16
2.	Many Muslims and Christians prefer dealing with people of their own religious groups to dealing with traditionalists in matters of trades and business.	3.56	3.50	3.83	10.89
3.	Many Muslims and Christians discriminate against traditionalists in the areas of job placement.	3.72	3.13	3.67	10.52

4.	Some Muslims and Christians patronise traditional practitioners for their own economic improvement and welfare.	3.86	3.63	3.77	11.26
5.	Many Muslims and Christians deny traditionalists access to means of labour such as land, capital, etc.	3.01	2.97	3.33	9.31
	Grand mean	3.51	3.29	3.62	10.42

Key: T=Traditionalist, M=Muslim, C= Christian

Based on the criterion mean of 2.5, it is clear from Table 3 that no item has mean value or grand mean value below 2.5, which means that members of the triadic religions agreed or strongly agreed that items 1 to 5 are indeed economic attitude to traditionalists in the pluralistic Nigerian society. However, item 4 (with cumulative mean values of 11.26) is the leading economic attitude of Muslims and Christians to traditionalists. The grand means further indicate that there is no significant difference in the opinions of these triadic religious believers on these items.

Research Question 3: What is the political attitude of the mosque and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society?

Table 4: Mean Rating of Respondents’ Opinions on Political Attitude in the pluralistic Nigerian society

N=45

s/no	Muslim and Christian attitudes to traditionalists	political	Mean Response		
	Item description	T	M	C	Total
1.	Many Muslims and Christians prefer people of their own religious groups rather than traditionalists to be appointed or elected into public offices.	3.14	3.50	3.50	10.14

2.	Many Muslims and Christians prefer people of their own religious groups rather than traditionalists to be appointed as traditional rulers/kings.	3.06	3.50	3.83	10.39
3.	Both Islam and Christianity compete with each other to Islamise and Christianise the traditionalists, including traditional throne.	3.56	2.83	3.17	9.56
4.	The government sponsor Muslims and Christians on pilgrimage and leave out traditionalists.	3.06	3.83	3.17	10.06
5.	Islamic and Christian religions and their clergy are more recognised and patronised by government than traditional priests.	3.81	2.97	3.33	10.11
	Grand mean	3.32	3.32	3.40	10.05

Key: T=Traditionalist, M=Muslim, C= Christian

Based on the criterion mean of 2.5, it is clear from Table 3 that no item has mean value or grand mean value below 2.5, which means that members of the triadic religions agreed or strongly agreed that items 1 to 5 are indeed political attitude to traditionalists in the pluralistic Nigerian society. However, item 2 (with cumulative mean values of 10.39) is the leading political attitude of Muslims and Christians to traditionalists. The grand means further indicate that there is no significant difference in the opinions of these triadic religious believers on these items.

Research Question 4: What is the social attitude of the mosques and church to the shrine in the pluralistic Nigeria society?

Table 5: Mean Rating of Respondents' Response on Social Attitude in the pluralistic Nigerian society

N=45

s/no	Muslim and Christian attitudes to traditionalists	social	Mean rating)	Response	(mean
	Item description	T	M	C	Total

1.	Many Muslims and Christians would not allow their children to marry traditionalists and vice versa.	2.98	3.12	3.37	9.47
2.	Many Muslims and Christians would not observe or participate in traditional religious festivals.	2.55	2.51	3.15	8.21
3.	Many Muslim and Christian landlords would not accommodate traditionalists as tenants.	2.61	2.72	3.48	8.81
4.	Many Muslims and Christians would not send their children to traditional faith-based schools.	3.17	3.56	3.78	10.51
5.	Many Muslim and Christian would not keep friendship with traditionalists.	2.83	3.01	3.61	9.45
Grand mean		2.82	2.98	3.47	9.29

Key: T=Traditionalist, M=Muslim, C= Christian

Based on the criterion mean of 2.5, it is clear from Table 5 that no item has mean value or grand mean value below 2.5, which means that members of the triadic religions agreed or strongly agreed that items 1 to 5 are indeed social attitude to traditionalists in the pluralistic Nigerian society. However, item 2 (with cumulative mean values of 10.51) is the leading social attitude of Muslims and Christians to traditionalists. The grand means further indicate that there is no significant difference in the opinions of these triadic religious believers on these items.

Discussion of Findings

Interestingly, all the twenty items of the four research questions are endorsed by majority of the respondents. The leading findings of the study are as follows. Many Muslims and Christians treat traditionalists as pagans. Some Muslims and Christians patronise traditional practitioners for economic improvement and welfare. Many Muslims and Christians prefer people of their own religious groups rather than traditionalists to be

appointed as traditional rulers/kings. Many Muslims and Christians would not send their children to traditional faith-based schools.

These findings have been corroborated by scholars like E.B. Idowu (1973), J.O. Awolalu and P.A. Dopamu (1979) and K.O. Opoku (1978) who asserted that many writers have misunderstood traditional religion by trying to define it under misleading terminologies such as animism, fetishism, magic, superstitions, primitive religion, ancestor worship, paganism, heathenism, idolatry, witchcraft and wizard, juju practice, magic, etc. They also declared that Muslims and Christians secretly patronise traditional practitioners (thaumaturgical response). Based on their findings on the interface, interlock and interactions among the triadic religion, the duo of Nabofa (1991) and Dopamu (1986) assert that there are adequate interactions among these triadic religious believers in virtually all facets of life, a stance that seem to disprove the findings that many Muslims and Christians prefer people of their own religious groups rather than traditionalists to be appointed into public offices in general and as traditional rulers/kings in particular. Their stance also seems to disprove the findings that many Muslims and Christians would not send their children to traditional faith-based schools, which are emerging trend in Yorubaland.

Challenges and Way forward

It is noteworthy that each of the twenty items of the research questions received respondents' (strong) agreement; hence, all the twenty items of the research questions constitute the challenges of Islam and Christianity against traditional religion in contemporary pluralistic Nigerian society. With the exception of Muslim and Christian compromisers, the challenges posed by mosque (Muslims) and church (Christians) against the shrine (traditionalists) are as follows. Mosque and church regard the shrine as paganism, dead religion, religion to be extirpated, condemned but at the same patronised in times of serious life problems that defy medical solution. The duo of mosque and church is indisposed to lending money or helping hands to the shrine, or buy goods from them, or recommend them for job, or sell land to them. Mosque and church appoint people of their group to public office with a view to Christianize or islamise the shrine, traditional thrones and institutions; mosque and church deny shrine government pilgrimage sponsorship, and discriminate against traditional priesthood in terms of government recognition and patronage. The duo of mosque and church still

frown at the idea of inter-religious marriage with the shrine (traditionalists); dissociate from traditional festival observation; would neither take traditionalists as tenants nor make friendship with them and would not patronise traditional based schools.

In other for the paper to be found non-guilty of religious bias, it should be stressed that the shrine (traditionalists) is also very capable of exhibiting all the aforementioned religious, economic, political and social attitudes against the mosque and church. In fact, it can be said without fear of contradiction that the shrine is equally guilty of the aforementioned religious attitudes against the mosque and church to some degree as there are some recorded cases (in the past and present time) in which the shrine was hostile to the mosque and church. Nonetheless, the duo of Islam and Christianity are usually more aggressive and provocative than the traditionalists in the contemporary pluralistic Nigerian society, which informs our present stance in this paper.

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations seem to be pertinent. There should be no compulsion or competition in religion. The triadic religions should jettison their hitherto “crude and unspiritual” methods of conversion characterised by acrimony, bitterness, hostility, and even blood-shed. More specifically, they should not regard each other as pagans but as believers in same God who could be worshipped in different ways as provided and recommended by different religions. People should respect the religion of others. People should be open to the knowledge of other religions in order to appreciate other people’s beliefs as well as our own. Religious attitude of exclusivism, being a disservice to religious harmony, cooperation and tolerance, must be abandoned in a pluralistic society.

Freedom of religion should be disseminated informally and formally. Religious hate speech against any religion should be discouraged. Inter-religious dialogue of life, social engagement, and religious experience should be promoted. Inter-faith based Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) should be encouraged by government. Religious leaders should embrace the tolerant attitude of inclusivism rather than the divisive attitude of exclusivism. Religious education should be acquired by all because most of the world’s religious extremism, intolerance and conflicts spring from religious ignorance. It is hard if not impossible to find traditionalist occupying Islamic or Christian “thrones” (positions), hence, it is proper to

recommend that traditional thrones (positions) should be reserved for persons who are traditionalists by religion. Government should be impartial in matters of religion. Nigerians should imbibe the national ethical principle of religious tolerance. Above all, Nigerians should love one another, irrespective of tribe and religion.

Conclusion

This paper has examined the interface, interlock and interaction among traditional religion, Islam and Christianity and has demonstrated the joint collaboration of the last two against the first. Despite claims of considerable interaction among the triadic religions by some authors, this paper's findings on the religious, economic, political and social attitudes of Islam and Christianity against traditional religion have indicated existence of some level of stigmatization, discrimination, and hostility against the traditional religion in our contemporary pluralistic Nigerian society. Hostility among these triadic religions can be reduced if not totally eliminated when adherents shun religious attitude of exclusivism/particularism and in its place embrace the religious attitudes of inclusivism, pluralism and parallelism.

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